

Brazil-Turkey Relations - a role theoretical analysis of emerging powers

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Acknowledgements

After having worked in Turkey for a political foundation and an international think tank for roughly eight years mainly on domestic issues, I decided to go academic again and do a PhD. What was clear then, was that it shouldn't have to do anything with domestic politics. The rest was everything but clear. In this phase, the debate on emerging powers caught my interest. The initial idea was to compare Brazil, Turkey and Germany in a study on emerging and established regional powers.

After professor Detlef Nolte in principle accepted to supervise this thesis, he not only suggested to reduce it to just two countries, but also helped finding the theoretic framework and directed my attention to important issues like status. I therefore would like to express my sincere gratitude and appreciation to my thesis advisor, also for many contacts and ideas concerning the interviews in Brazil and a very good cooperation over the course of the thesis preparation and writing.

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1. Introduction

The 2000s were (tagged as) the golden years for emerging powers. Led by the BRICS and followed by a plethora of less known groupings such as MINT, Next-11, MIKTA or CIVETS, scenarios of a “post-western” world were high on the agenda of both economists and political scientists. Especially during the time of the global financial crisis 2008/09 the change of the global order as we knew it, seemed almost palpable. The clear protagonist of this movement is China, but Brazil and Turkey are in a subsequent group of countries representing this trend. The BRICS also became a darling for academics. Research centers around the world flourished to describe and compare them, but there is significantly less research between BRICS and non-BRICS emerging powers. Therefore this thesis will offer new insights into relations of emerging powers, also on a cross-regional basis.

However, not only this aspect is novel. The bilateral Brazil-Turkey relations in general are a little researched topic with still an exotic flair. After all, in the past 12 years there have been at least a few preliminary studies on the historic relations in the form of books and dissertations and some articles on aspects of bilateral relations. Therefore with this study still many firsts will be covered and some aspects will be examined in an unprecedented depth. Among the firsts is a detailed description of the historic relations in the 19th century in English, which until now only partly exists in either Turkish or Portuguese. This thesis merges research in the two languages. Further firsts are the chapters on cultural and academic relations. Most articles so far dealt with the 2010 Iran Declaration. Here a very detailed account will be presented taking into account recent written sources in several languages, as is the case for the economic and politico-diplomatic chapters. Since there is little written material about the topical state of bilateral relations, numerous interviews were conducted throughout 2016 in both Turkey and Brazil. This enriches the thesis with so far unpublished aspects of bilateral relations and gives the thesis a further depth.

Broadly speaking the thesis is divided into two main parts and several sub-chapters. The first part includes theoretical chapters and aspects of the foreign policies of Brazil and Turkey. The second part is about several aspects of the bilateral relations.

The theoretic frame is role theory, which has been used in foreign policy analysis since 1970. According to it, foreign policy is not decided spontaneously on a case-basis, but follows road-maps, which are based on the available resources of a state and the role formulation of decision makers. Therefore it is a theory combining structure and agency. To best analyze and compare foreign policy performances, ideal types are developed. In our case the ideal type is that of emerging powers, which is equivalent to rising powers. However, in carving out the role of these states, also regional and middle powers are taken into account, which are researched in more detail. Brazil and Turkey will be defined as both emerging powers until 2013 and new middle powers since then. Additionally both states are also part of the small category of cusp states, which are characterized as not only geographically lying at the edge of a region, but more importantly having an ambivalent relation to their home region from a historic and political perspective and suffer from problems of recognition. This cuspness of Brazil and Turkey could further increase the desire to strengthen relations with other emerging powers outside the home region.

Brazil and Turkey by and large fulfill the pre-conditions of emerging powers to dominate their neighbors in economic, diplomatic, military and soft power categories. This is more

obvious with Brazil, but also Turkey is in most categories either leading or in second position, but taken all together also a clear candidate for leadership in a given region, in this case the Middle East.

However, resources are not enough. Equally important is that such a role conception is also formulated by leading decision makers. Therefore these role formulations will be analyzed in both countries from speeches, interviews and written articles or books by leading decision makers. Decisive role formulations would mention to develop a global foreign policy not confined to one region, the importance of trade, economic and investment aspects of foreign policy, to forge alliances with other emerging powers, to launch diplomatic initiatives of global importance or to challenge the current order be it in trade or in diplomatic negotiations. Some of these formulations can be very explicit, others will be more indirect. Especially two motivations are important for the intensification of relations: emerging powers try to raise their status in the global diplomatic hierarchy and are searching for new trade options for their ever more export-oriented economies.

The second part of the first block is a brief analysis of the foreign policies of Brazil and Turkey after the end of the Cold War. Since this is a far too broad subject, only the most important features of especially the AKP (Justice and Development Party) and PT (Workers' Party) foreign policies will be analyzed. Besides this, a few selected foreign policy issues will be looked at, which can be compared, such as whether the AKP/PT foreign policies represent a rupture with foreign policy traditions or rather a continuation of former foreign policy practices. Another sub-chapter deals with the use of soft power in both countries' foreign policies.

The second part of the thesis then describes and analyzes how these two emerging powers intensify their relations in political, economic, cultural and academic fields. Does the bilateral example correspond to the role formulation of emerging power. However, before getting to the contemporary relations, the section begins with the historic relations in the 19th until the early 20th century. The first diplomatic contacts already started in the 1850s leading to a first bilateral treaty signed in 1858. Most of the aims of the treaty, direct trade relations, setting up of diplomatic missions or more independence from European powers were not achieved. However, already then two peripheral powers tried to become more independent from the big economic powers of the time and strengthen their direct relations. Towards the end of the 19th century, the question of migration of Ottoman citizens to Brazil both led to more contacts and connections, but was also a source of problems and accusations. The 1858 treaty was finally abolished in 1912. It lasted until 1927 until the young Turkish Republic and Brazil signed again a friendship treaty, this time however, without mentioning any economic or political goals. That seemed a wise prevision. The bilateral relations during the Cold War are largely a terra incognita. There were embassies in both countries, but no state visits and only very little economic exchange. This only changed in the 1990s when the first state visits happened and Turkey for the first time formulated a Latin America strategy where Brazil would be the major partner. These first initiatives however, had to be postponed because of domestic problems in both countries in the late 1990s and early 2000s. Therefore the real intensification of bilateral relations only happened during the AKP governments and PT presidencies, which began almost simultaneously in late 2002 and early 2003 respectively. Contacts were continuously intensified and state visits of the highest level took place to both countries. The climax of diplomatic-political relations was in 2010 when the two countries tried to broker a deal concerning the Iranian nuclear program and signed a comprehensive strategic partnership. However, both the Iranian Declaration was not successful and the many concrete plans from the strategic partnership were not realized. With the climax in relations also the decline of intensity began mainly caused by rising domestic problems. In Brazil these were economic difficulties, corruption scandals and mass riots and in Turkey to a lesser degree also rising

domestic problems but especially growing insecurities caused by the wars in Syria and Iraq, terrorism in Turkey and refugee flows, which forced both countries to focus on domestic issues and the near environment. Therefore, independently from the bilateral relations, both countries in general have retreated from the international scene in the past five years. The political relations with less intensity remain good with one exception, the Armenian Genocide, which the Brazilian Senate commemorated in 2015. Since this was only a limited motion, this topic might cause diplomatic disgruntlements again in the future when the Chamber of Deputies will vote on an already planned and much more comprehensive recognition.

Parallel to the political relations, also the economic and trade relations developed strongly under the AKP/PT legislatures, but only until 2011. As in the politico-diplomatic chapter also some economic aspects will be compared, which feature prominent in both countries such as corruption and inequality. The bilateral trade volume increased since 2003 eight times until 2011 to reach almost three billion USD. However, then it was expected to soon increase to ten billion, whereas it declined to currently only slightly above two billion USD. The main reason for the decline is the economic crisis in Brazil, but also negative experiences of exporters and investors in the two countries and that the economic relations still have to be regarded as new. The market conditions, right contacts and networks are little known. This is also the reason why investments in both countries are low, only a few companies dared to commit to a bigger investment. An exceptional development could be witnessed in tourism, which has increased enormously, but only by Brazilian tourists to Turkey, not the other way around. Since the economic and financial crisis in Brazil will continue at least until 2018, it cannot be expected that the bilateral trade relations will increase before this crisis is overcome.

To conclude, two more aspects of bilateral relations are analyzed, the academic and the cultural relations. Both remain on a low level, also negatively affected by the domestic and economic problems in Brazil. Concerning the cultural relations, since 2006 the controversial Turkish-Islamic Gülen network has been active in Brazil with a school, cultural centre and a chamber of commerce. However, since the Gülenists and the Turkish government are in open confrontation since December 2013 and even more so since July 2016, this also reduced the financial means and room of manoeuvre of the Gülen movement in Brazil. So far there is no state or other privately sponsored cultural activities on a comparable level. In Turkey, Brazilian cultural associations are run by private persons only and therefore with far lower financial means and staff. This low level of cultural exchange is also due to the fact that very few Turks live in Brazil and Brazilians in Turkey. Not even 1000 citizens each reside permanently in the other country.

Concerning academic relations, there are currently three university centers in Turkey dealing with Latin America. Two of them were launched during the most intensive period of bilateral relations. In Brazil until today there is no Turkish studies or similar department. A recent development is that the Brazilian university association Grupo Coimbra started to connect with Turkish universities signing cooperation agreements. However, due to the insecure situation in Turkey, the student exchange so far did not materialize.

In all aspects of bilateral relations an increase in intensity could be witnessed until 2010/2011. Both countries practiced the role of emerging power in strengthening relations with another emerging power, increasing the trade volume and political contacts and engaging in diplomatic initiatives of global interest. This was also a time of constant economic growth, domestic stability with governments and presidencies of very high approval ratings. However, since then there is a process of de-intensification, which also hints at the limits of what emerging

powers can reach in bilateral relations and international diplomacy when domestic problems arise. In the end they didn't prove to be so crisis-resistant as predicted during the global financial crisis in 2008/09. They also lack the physical and human capacities to sustain such an ambitious foreign policy in times of domestic or neighborhood crises. Interestingly, even if this process now has been going on for roughly five years, no adjusting of the role conception could be witnessed. Decision makers still formulate the same active and global foreign policy as ten years ago, whereas the actual policies do not match anymore these ambitions. The retreat from the international scene and the slowdown in bilateral relations is not matched by the role conceptions.

The thesis is written in American English. All translations were done by the author. All links were controlled again between 10 and 13 October 2016.